

BARREL MUON TRACK RECONSTRUCTION AT CMS LEVEL-1 TRIGGER USING DEEP LEARNING

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AUTHOR(S):

Fabio Cufino
TU Dortmund University

CMS Collaboration

SUPERVISOR(S):

Rocco Ardino
Thomas Owen James

Abstract

The CMS Level-1 (L1) Trigger executes rapid (under 3 microseconds) reconstruction using FPGA logic on a subset of detector data at the 40 MHz bunch-crossing rate, selecting approximately 100 kHz of the most interesting events for full readout and processing in the software filter farm. The L1 Scouting system introduces a novel data-taking paradigm, capturing L1 information at the full 40 MHz rate, enabling analyses with minimal selection bias and greater flexibility for studying rare or unexpected phenomena.

This project uses machine learning techniques to implement a robust real-time data quality and system integrity monitoring solution, ensuring precise oversight of FPGA operations within L1 Scouting. The integration of these methods supports efficient and reliable operation of the system, enabling detailed physics analyses under high-luminosity conditions.

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1 Introduction

The Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) experiment is one of the primary multi-purpose detectors at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). The LHC, colliding proton bunches at a nominal frequency of 40 MHz, generates an immense volume of collision data, necessitating an efficient system to process and filter this information. To achieve this, CMS employs a dual-tiered trigger system designed for event selection. The initial tier, known as the Level-1 trigger (L1T), is hardware-based and utilizes algorithms with fixed latency to perform basic object reconstruction, primarily focusing on data from calorimeters and the muon system to discard events that are unlikely to be of physical interest. After a successful L1T selection, the full detector is read out, and the raw data is sent to the subsequent tier, the High-Level Trigger (HLT). HLT uses software to conduct the online reconstruction, leveraging the full array of detector information to select events that meet specific criteria [5].

Given the sheer volume of data produced by the detector, the CMS trigger system must implement selection criteria to target a generic set of interesting signature. While this approach increases the probability of capturing known physics processes, it runs the risk of excluding potentially rare phenomena. To address this, data scouting has been introduced as a method for extracting less-filtered event information directly from the trigger system, offering a broader scope for analysis.

As the LHC prepares for its High-Luminosity (HL-LHC) phase, expected to begin later this decade, substantial upgrades are being implemented across the CMS experiment, particularly within the trigger system. These upgrades aim to maintain and extend the standard CMS physics program under larger pileup conditions at the price of an increase in the L1 accept rate from approximately 100 kHz to 750 kHz. The Level-1 trigger will undergo significant changes, incorporating advanced algorithms and reading out particle tracks from the tracker back-end, with the goal of achieving near-offline reconstruction quality at 40 MHz [2], [13]. This development makes Level-1 trigger Data Scouting (L1DS) particularly relevant.

L1DS is poised to play a crucial role in future physics analyses by providing data that is nearly unbiased, providing a promising ground for real-time analysis and anomaly detection applications. In preparation for these HL-LHC operations, the CMS collaboration has developed a Run-3 demonstrator for the L1DS system. This platform is designed to be compatible with the current trigger system architecture and serves as a testing ground for scouting strategies, hardware configurations, and data extraction techniques in anticipation of the upcoming upgrades.

The report explores the application of machine learning techniques to reconstruct muon tracks from segments based on super-primitives (or *stubs*) which are processed by the Twin-Mux and delivered to the Barrel Muon Track Finder (BMTF), evaluating their potential for integration into the enhanced L1DS system planned for future high-luminosity operations.

2 The CMS experiment at the Large Hadron Collider

The Large Hadron Collider (LHC), situated at CERN in Geneva, Switzerland, resides within a 27 Km tunnel buried 100 meters underground. Operational since 2010, the LHC is capable of accelerating protons and heavy-ion beams to reach a center-of-mass energy up to 13.6 TeV [4]. The procedure of injecting protons into the LHC is facilitated by a sequence of accelerators, which enable an injection energy of 450 GeV into the collider. The typical beam structure comprises 39 trains, each containing 72 bunches with $N = 1.1 \times 10^{11}$ protons. Operating at a crossing frequency of 40 MHz, the setup results in an inter-collision interval of 25 ns. At the LHC's nominal instantaneous luminosity, $L_{\text{inst}} = 2 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, multiple proton-proton

interactions occur in a single bunch crossing, a phenomenon referred to as 'pile-up.' Under these conditions, the LHC achieves an average pile-up of approximately 60 interactions per bunch crossing.

Collisions are managed at four specific interaction points within the accelerator ring, where the main experiments of the LHC—ATLAS, CMS, ALICE, and LHCb—are situated.

The CMS - Compact Muon Solenoid - is one of the four pivotal detectors operational at the LHC. It serves as a versatile detector, designed with multiple concentric layers, each aimed at capturing and analyzing distinct properties of the particles generated from high-energy collisions. The CMS detector is equipped with various subsystems:

- A **Silicon Tracker**, sensitive to charged particles, enabling the reconstruction of their trajectories.
- An **Electromagnetic Calorimeter (ECAL)**, which measures the energy of electrons and photons.
- A **Hadronic Calorimeter (HCAL)**, which measures the energy of hadrons.
- A **Superconducting Solenoid**, producing a 3.8 T magnetic field, which bends the paths of charged particles in the transverse plane, allowing their momentum to be measured.
- A **Muon System**, designed to capture muon tracks, consisting of Drift Tubes (DTs), Cathode Strip Chambers (CSCs), Resistive Plate Chambers (RPCs) and Gaseous Electron Multipliers (GEMs).

Figure 1 showcases the diverse subdetectors mentioned and other components [15].

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the CMS detector [9]

3 CMS Level-1 Trigger and Data Scouting

The CMS Trigger System is pivotal in the data acquisition process, as it reduces the vast amount of collision data generated at a frequency of 40 MHz to a manageable offline storage rate of approximately 1 kHz [10]. This reduction is essential due to the limitations in readout and storage capabilities. The trigger system consists of two main components: the Level-1 Trigger and the High-Level Trigger. The L1T, built with custom electronics, prioritizes swift decision-making by utilizing coarse-grained muon detectors and calorimeter data to decrease the event readout rate to 100 kHz. In contrast, the HLT is software-driven and operates on a dedicated processor farm. It leverages detailed information from all subdetectors, including the silicon inner tracker, to enable a more thorough analysis of events.

3.1 L1 Trigger

The L1T [8] system is designed to evaluate each bunch crossing and determine whether events should be retained for further analysis. It consists of local, regional, and global triggers, each contributing to a structured decision-making process. Local Triggers, or Trigger Primitive Generators (TPGs), identify candidates by analyzing energy deposits in calorimeter towers and hit patterns in muon chambers. Regional Triggers aggregate this information, applying spatial pattern logic to assess and rank the trigger objects, such as muon candidates, based on parameters like energy and momentum. The final decision is made by the Global Trigger (GT), which employs algorithms to determine if an event meets the criteria for further analysis, producing a Level-1 Accept (L1A) signal if the conditions are met. This process is performed within a 4-microsecond window, relying on custom hardware, including FPGAs and LUTs, to ensure timely operation. Within this framework, the Muon and Calorimeter Triggers perform specific roles.

Figure 2 showcases a schematic representation of the Muon and Calorimeter Triggers.

Figure 2: Diagram of the upgraded CMS Level-1 trigger system during Run 2 [12]

The Muon Trigger system is designed to accurately track muons across different regions of the detector. It is divided into three subsystems, each targeting distinct η ranges: the Barrel Muon Track Finder (BMTF), the Overlap Muon Track Finder (OMTF), and the Endcap Muon Track Finder (EMTF). These subsystems process Trigger Primitives (TPs) generated from the CSCs, DTs, and RPCs.

CSCs provide TPs to the EMTF and OMTF via a mezzanine on the muon port card, while RPC hits from the endcaps are processed through the Concentrator Pre-Processor and Fan-out (CPPF) card. Barrel RPC and DT TPs are routed to the TwinMux concentrator card, which combines the precise spatial resolution of DT segments with the timing characteristics of RPC hits to produce super-primitives, that are track segments made from combining hits in both the drift tube and resistive plate chamber sections of the detector. These refined data are then utilized by the BMTF and OMTF to enhance muon candidate identification.

The system maintains redundancy by using multiple detection chambers, with additional stations extending coverage up to $|\eta| = 2.8$.

The final step involves the Global Muon Trigger (GMT) that eliminates duplicates, arranges muons, selects the top eight muon candidates, which are then forwarded to the Global Trigger (GT) for further analysis.

3.2 Data Scouting

The L1 Data Scouting system introduces a novel approach to data collection by capturing intermediate data directly from the L1 trigger at the full 40 MHz bunch crossing rate. This allows for the analysis of high-frequency event types that are typically too common to be included in the standard L1 trigger menu. Notably, L1DS operates independently of the L1 trigger decision-making process, meaning it does not influence the outcomes of the trigger.

Figure 3: CMS Level-1 (L1) scouting scheme [6]

With L1DS, it's possible to perform semi-real-time analysis using L1 trigger objects or store compact event records. Additionally, the system enhances diagnostic and monitoring capabilities, providing BX-to-BX correlations and enabling independent per-bunch luminosity measurements.

3.2.1 The CMS Run-3 Level-1 Data Scouting Demonstrator

A L1DS demonstrator has been set up for Run-3. This demonstrator enables event analysis directly at the L1T stage by capturing data at the full 40 MHz bunch crossing rate, independent of the primary L1 trigger decision-making process.

Figure 4 shows the scheme for the L1DS demonstrator.

Figure 4: The CMS Run-3 Level-1 Data Scouting demonstrator architecture.

The architecture of the L1DS demonstrator integrates several layers and components designed to optimize the capture and processing of data streams from the L1T system. The system is set up to draw data from at various stages of the L1 trigger, specifically from the Global Trigger, Global Muon Trigger, Calorimeter, and Barrel Muon Track Finder, with details illustrated in Table 1.

To manage the drawn data efficiently, the L1DS system is built on a foundation of high-bandwidth data paths. These paths employ 10 Gb/s trigger link protocols to rapidly transmit raw data from the trigger systems.

The system utilizes 100 Gb/s Ethernet connections for the output link between the FPGA boards and the Data Scouting Buffer Units (DSBUs) located on the surface, ensuring the swift transfer of data necessary to handle the enormous volumes generated..

At the heart of the data processing within the L1DS system are Xilinx VCU128 FPGA boards, which feature the powerful Ultrascale+ XCVU37P FPGA. These boards are tasked with processing the data at high speeds, leveraging their GTY transceivers and multiple QSFP ports for high-bandwidth connectivity. The VCU128 boards also include 8 GB of High Bandwidth Memory (HBM), which serves as a large temporary buffer for the data, later transmitted via TCP/IP through 100 GbE links to the Data Scouting Buffer Units (DSBUs) for further processing [11].

As the data moves through the system, after the FPGA boards, it first reaches the Data Scouting Buffer Units (DSBUs). These units are designed to temporarily store the data streams coming from the scouting boards, performing basic processing and preparing the data fragments to be injected into the Data Scouting Processing Units for more intensive processing.

Input system	N 10Gb/s links	Objects
GMT	4	Up to 8 GMT muons
Calorimeter trigger	7 + 1 spare	e/γ , tau candidates, jets and energy sums including E_T^{miss}
BMTF	24	BMTF input super primitives
GT	18	Algorithm bits

Table 1: Inputs to the L1DS demonstrator.

Following this initial buffering, the data is processed by the DSPUs. These units unpack the raw data fragments produced by the DSBU and aggregate them into collections designed for efficient storage. Additionally, they perform online analysis on the aggregated data to identify sets of BXs that meet specific analysis requirements. These analysis processes produce a set of BXs that meet the criteria, and the filtered BXs are stored in an additional data stream. The main data stream, called the ZeroBias stream, contains unpacked data that has not been filtered or analyzed and is prescaled to limit total output throughput. Finally, the processed data is temporarily stored in the Lustre Cluster File System, which is used as intermediate storage before being moved to the Tier-0 for repacking and permanent storage in the CMS Data Aggregation System.

TwinMux System in the CMS Level-1 Muon Trigger Upgrade The TwinMux system is a key component of the upgraded Level-1 (L1) muon trigger system for the CMS experiment, particularly in the barrel region of the detector. Serving as a “barrel concentrator”, the TwinMux boards aggregate and process data from DTs and RPCs muon detection subsystems. The system consists of 60 TwinMux boards strategically deployed to handle inputs from these different subdetectors and ensure efficient data processing and transmission to the BMTF.

Each TwinMux board is equipped to handle inputs from both DTs and RPCs, converting and concentrating the lower-speed optical trigger links into higher-speed links that are sent to the BMTF and Overlap Muon Track Finder (OMTF). This conversion is crucial for managing the high data rates required by the upgraded CMS trigger system. By concentrating data into fewer, faster links, TwinMux helps to streamline the transmission process, reducing the number of physical connections needed and increasing the system’s reliability and performance under high-luminosity conditions [16]. A picture of a TwinMux board is showed in Figure 5.

Figure 5: TwinMux board picture

The generation of super-primitives begins by receiving input data from DT and RPC links from one sector of the barrel muon detector. DT data consists of trigger segments, including position, direction, quality, and bunch crossing (BX) information, while RPC data consists of hits, including position and BX information.

The process begins by aligning the incoming data in time to ensure proper synchronization. A clustering algorithm is then applied to group neighboring signals from the RPC detector into clusters, which are converted into coordinates compatible with the DT system. To prevent duplicate information, clusters that occur in consecutive time intervals are filtered out.

Next, the algorithm identifies clusters that are close in position to DT Trigger Segments. The closest cluster is selected, and if the difference in their angles is within a pre-defined range, the two are considered matched. When a match is found, a quality indicator, known as the SuperPrimitive quality bit, is assigned to reflect the association.

If the DT Trigger Segment was constructed using fewer than 8 DT ϕ layers, its BX is shifted to match the RPC cluster BX. If no match with an RPC cluster is found, the original DT Trigger Segment is sent to the Barrel Muon Track Finder (BMTF), and the SuperPrimitive quality bit is not set [7].

The TwinMux boards are capable of generating up to two super-primitives per muon station. These are then forwarded to the BMTF processors, which implement a specialized hardware algorithm to efficiently convert super-primitives into track candidates (see the following section for further details). Additionally, super-primitives from the external wheels near the endcaps are duplicated and sent to the Overlap Muon Track Finder (OMTF) processors.

Each of the 12 BMTF boards, one dedicated to each wedge, receives super-primitives from the TwinMux boards and can handle up to eight stubs per wedge. The TwinMux system produces up to two stubs for each of the four stations in a wedge.

The BMTF inputs, or stubs, are extracted through a specialized scouting system that connects to each BMTF board via two dedicated links, for a total of 24 links. Each link can transfer up to 8 stubs, with the BMTF boards selecting the 'best' stubs based on quality and bending (lower bending indicating higher p_T). This process allows for a maximum of 96 high-quality stubs to be extracted per bunch crossing. These stubs are then directed to a Xilinx VCU128 board and subsequently forwarded to a data processing server for further analysis, as illustrated previously in Figure 4.

4 BMTF Track Reconstruction

The subsequent discussion addresses the methodology for muon candidate reconstruction. This task is managed online by the Muon Track Finder processors, with the BMTF boards specifically assigned to the barrel region of the detector. The BMTF boards employ a specialized hardware algorithm that efficiently translates super-primitives into track candidates. By integrating compatible segments from various detector stations within a designated extrapolation window, these boards effectively reconstruct muon tracks.

The previous discussion covered the role of BMTF processors in this context. This section offers a detailed examination of the BMTF hardware algorithm that facilitates real-time muon candidate reconstruction within the trigger system.

4.1 Kalman Filter

The Kalman filter [3] is an algorithm used in the CMS Barrel Muon Track Finder for the reconstruction of muon tracks within the detector. It operates by sequentially processing measurements from different detector stations, updating the estimated state of the muon track as new data becomes available. The Kalman filter is particularly well-suited for this application due to its ability to handle noisy data and to improve estimates of the track parameters as the muon passes through various layers of the detector.

The algorithm begins with an initial estimate of the state vector \mathbf{x}_0 , which includes parameters like the position ϕ , bending angle ϕ_b , and curvature $k = \frac{q}{p_T}$, where q is the charge and p_T is the transverse momentum:

$$\mathbf{x}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} \phi_0 \\ \phi_{b0} \\ k_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The uncertainties in these parameters are represented by an initial covariance matrix \mathbf{P}_0 .

The next step for the Kalman Filter is the Propagation. As the muon propagates through the detector from one station to the next, the state vector is updated using a propagation matrix \mathbf{F} that models the effects of the magnetic field and other factors:

$$\begin{pmatrix} k \\ \phi \\ \phi_b \end{pmatrix}_n = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ a & 1 & b \\ c & 0 & 1 - b \end{pmatrix}}_{\text{Propagation Matrix } \mathbf{F}} \begin{pmatrix} k \\ \phi \\ \phi_b \end{pmatrix}_{n-1} \quad (2)$$

with a, b, c that depend on the magnetic field and the dimensions and are different from station to station. It's worth to note that here the energy loss is neglected from station to station and this is added at the end.

The covariance matrix \mathbf{P} is also propagated to account for the increase in uncertainty and multiple scattering as the particle moves through the detector:

$$\mathbf{P}_n = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{P}_{n-1}\mathbf{F}^T + \mathbf{Q}(k, x/X_0) \quad (3)$$

When a new measurement \mathbf{z}_{n+1} is obtained from the detector, it is used to update the state vector and its covariance matrix. The residual r is then calculated using the following:

$$\mathbf{r}_n = \begin{pmatrix} \phi^{\text{stub}} \\ \phi_b^{\text{stub}} \end{pmatrix}_n - \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}}_{\text{Measurement Matrix } \mathbf{H}} \begin{pmatrix} k \\ \phi \\ \phi_b \end{pmatrix}_n \quad (4)$$

Next, the covariance matrix \mathbf{P}_n , which represents the uncertainties in the current estimate of the track's state, is transformed into the measurement space. This transformation is performed using the measurement matrix \mathbf{H} , and the transformed covariance is given by:

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}_n\mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R}$$

Here, \mathbf{R} represents the measurement noise, which accounts for the resolution of the detector's measurements.

The Kalman Gain \mathbf{K} is then computed, which determines how much the new measurement should influence the updated state estimate. This gain is derived from the transformed covariance \mathbf{S} and is used to update the state of the track:

$$\mathbf{x}_n^{\text{upd}} = \mathbf{x}_n + \underbrace{\mathbf{P}\mathbf{H}^T\mathbf{S}^{-1}}_{\text{Kalman Gain}} \mathbf{r}_n$$

By applying this update, the track's state is adjusted according to the residual, resulting in a more accurate estimate of the particle's trajectory. This iterative process ensures that the track is continuously refined as new measurements are obtained, improving the precision of the muon detection system.

This process of propagation and measurement update is repeated as the muon passes through each station of the detector. Each iteration refines the estimate of the muon's trajectory, improving the precision of the track reconstruction [3].

Special Considerations for FPGA Implementation: In FPGA implementations, the matrix operations required by the Kalman filter, such as matrix multiplication and inversion, are computationally intensive. To optimize performance, these operations are mapped to the DSP cores available on the FPGA. Additionally, pre-calculated values, such as the Kalman gain, can be stored in look-up tables (LUTs) to reduce the need for real-time computation, thereby optimizing resource usage and reducing latency.

By leveraging these techniques, the Kalman filter implemented in the BMTF can efficiently process the incoming data in real-time, providing accurate muon track reconstruction even under the high data throughput conditions of the CMS experiment.

5 Neural Networks for Muon Reconstruction

The Kalman filter has proven effective for real-time muon track reconstruction in the CMS BMTF, its reliance on strict hardware operations limits flexibility, particularly in high-throughput environments like the High Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC). To overcome these challenges, the CMS collaboration has begun exploring alternative approaches, including the use of machine learning algorithms. Specifically, this section explores the potential of High-Level Synthesis (HLS) tools, such as HLS4ML [14], to design Neural Networks (NN) that can be synthesized into FPGA hardware with the aim of surpassing the performance of the Level-1 trigger Kalman filter.

5.1 Dataset

To effectively train a machine learning algorithm for assigning physical attributes to input stubs, a specialized dataset has been developed. This dataset integrates *stub data* with details from *offline reconstruction*, providing a comprehensive basis for training.

The primary data source is a dataset that has been created using the ParticleGun tool to generate muons with a flat transverse momentum distribution ranging from 2 GeV to 100 GeV. The ParticleGun tool allows the generation of single muons with predefined properties, such as a flat p_T distribution. The generated data includes the relevant attributes for the neural network, such as the associated GMT muons, BMTF candidates, and kBMTF tracks.

To refine the dataset, several selection criteria were applied: events with $p_T^{L1} = 4.5$ GeV, $\eta^{\text{RECO}} > 1$ or $\eta^{\text{RECO}} < -1$, and $p_T^{\text{RECO}} < 4$ GeV were excluded.

The variables included in the dataset are listed in Table 2.

Description	Bits Used
Detector sector identifier	4 bits
Wheel number in the CMS detector	3 bits
Station number	2 bits
Quality of the stub	3 bits
Pseudorapidity variable 1 and 2	7 bits
Quality of η_1, η_2	7 bits
Flag for selecting η set	1 bit
Azimuthal angle	12 bits
Bending angle	10 bits

Table 2: Summary of Features and width in bits

It is important to note that each feature is uniquely associated with a specific station number of the stub. This correspondence stems from the dataset structure, which assumes a maximum of four stubs per event. If a stub is missing for a particular station, its corresponding slot is padded with default placeholder values.

The goal of this work is to predict the RECO muon's transverse momentum p_T , pseudorapidity η , azimuthal angle ϕ at the vertex, and the particle's charge.

It is important to note that the number of stubs associated with each RECO muon can vary, resulting in events with 2, 3, or 4 stubs per muon. This variability leads to inputs of different sizes for the neural network. To accommodate this, three distinct datasets were created: one for events with 2 stubs and 2×11 features, consisting of ≈ 860 k entries; another for events with 3 stubs and 3×11 features, containing ≈ 1.15 M entries; and a third for events with 4 stubs and 4×11 features, comprising ≈ 940 k entries.

Each dataset is used to train a separate neural network.

6 Neural Network Design and Implementation

Three distinct neural network architectures were designed, each corresponding to one of the three datasets. The networks are fully connected, feed-forward architectures optimized for seamless integration into the HLS4ML environment. Due to hardware constraints, the models are limited to a few thousand parameters, balancing performance with resource efficiency. The output layer of each network contains three neurons, corresponding to the three target attributes being predicted. Based on findings from [1], the ELU (Exponential Linear Unit) activation function was selected for the output neurons, as it demonstrated superior performance compared to other functions such as ReLU and GELU.

The design includes a mechanism for recovering the particle's charge by utilizing the sign of the transverse momentum, enabling the reconstruction of the particle's charge by simply predict the sign of the momentum, as well as η and ϕ . The model's performance is evaluated using regression loss metrics, with Mean Absolute Error (MAE) being the primary metric. To enhance the model's robustness and prevent overfitting, L2 regularization with a strength of $\lambda = 10^{-3}$ is incorporated into the network training process. This regularization strategy ensures that the model generalizes well to unseen data while maintaining high accuracy on the training set.

A schematic representation of the three neural network architectures used in this study is shown in Table 3. Each table in the figure represents the structure of the three different neural network used, detailing the number of neurons and layers in each.

Layer	N° of Neurons	Layer	N° of Neurons	Layer	N° of Neurons
Input	22	Input	33	Input	44
Hidden	32, 32, 16, 8	Hidden	64, 32, 32, 32	Hidden	16, 16, 16, 8
Output	4	Output	4	Output	4

Table 3: Schematic of the three neural network architectures used in this study, specifically for 2 input stubs NN, 3 input stubs NN, and 4 input stubs NN.

Following the methodology outlined in [1], the datasets were divided into training, validation, and testing sets with a distribution of 63% for training, 7% for validation, and 30% for testing. Mini-batch training was employed, with batch size optimized for both training speed and consistency. The ADAM optimizer was selected, with an initial learning rate η set to 10^{-2} , controlled by a custom scheduler that halved the rate when validation loss improved by less than 5% over five epochs. Early stopping was implemented after 60 epochs if the validation loss improved by less than 0.001% over ten epochs.

To improve training efficiency and prevent large weight penalties due to L2 regularization, each feature was normalized using powers of 2. Although this approach is unconventional in typical machine learning, it is a simple yet effective implementation of feature normalization tailored for FPGA logic, enabling neural network inference to be performed online. Features with only positive values were normalized to a range of approximately 0 to 1, while features covering both positive and negative values were adjusted to a range of about -1 to 1.

The training and validation losses for the three neural networks are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Regression loss curves for training and validation datasets across different stub counts: (a) 2 stubs, (b) 3 stubs, and (c) 4 stubs.

6.1 Results

As previously described, the charge information from the dataset was incorporated into the charge reconstruction process to assign a sign to the predicted transverse momentum. This enables the neural networks to output a signed transverse momentum, reflecting the particle's charge, and eliminates the need for a separate classification task in the final layer of the neural network architectures.

The charge reconstruction accuracy for all three neural networks shows a slight improvement over the L1 predictions. In particular, the neural network utilizing 2 stubs achieves a charge reconstruction accuracy that is 1.17% higher than the L1 predictions. The detailed accuracy results are presented in Table 4.

Dataset	NN Charge Accuracy [%]	L1 Charge Accuracy [%]
2 Stubs	99.14	97.97
3 Stubs	99.42	99.09
4 Stubs	99.45	99.26

Table 4: Comparison of charge reconstruction accuracy between neural networks (NNs) and L1 predictions for different stub configurations.

Beside the reconstruction of the charge, the neural networks predicted also the transverse momentum, the ϕ and the η .

To evaluate the neural networks' performance in reconstructing these quantities, the resolution for transverse momentum was defined as $\Delta p_T/p^{\text{RECO}}$, where $\Delta p_T = p_T - p^{\text{RECO}}$. The residuals for ϕ and η were defined as $\Delta\phi = \phi - \phi^{\text{RECO}}$ and $\Delta\eta = \eta - \eta^{\text{RECO}}$, respectively. These metrics provide a measure of the deviation between the predicted values and the corresponding reconstructed values, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of the neural networks' reconstruction capabilities.

Figure 7 presents the transverse momentum reconstruction resolution for both the machine learning method and the traditional Kalman Filter approach used by the BM TF. A notable difference in resolution is attributed to a deliberate miscalibration in the Level-1 trigger. Specifically, the reconstruction algorithm assigns a transverse momentum value approximately 1.2 times higher than the true physical value. This intentional miscalibration of p_T has been used to improve trigger efficiency across a broad range of p_T .

Figure 8 and 9 illustrates the residuals for η and ϕ respectively, for both methods. In each case, the predictions generated by the neural network demonstrate better performance than

Figure 7: Transverse momentum reconstruction resolution for the machine learning method (NN reconstruction) and the traditional Kalman Filter approach (L1) used by the BMTF. The plots show the comparison for neural networks using (a) 2 stubs, (b) 3 stubs, and (c) 4 stubs.

Figure 8: Residuals of pseudorapidity (η) for the neural network (NN) reconstruction and the traditional Kalman Filter approach (L1) for different stub configurations: (a) 2 stubs, (b) 3 stubs, and (c) 4 stubs.

Figure 9: Residuals of azimuthal angle (ϕ) for the neural network (NN) reconstruction and the traditional Kalman Filter approach (L1) for different stub configurations: (a) 2 stubs, (b) 3 stubs, and (c) 4 stubs. The NN reconstruction achieves better performance compared to the conventional method, particularly at higher stub counts.

those produced by the conventional approach.

Specifically, the neural network predictions result in narrower and more centralized distributions, indicating higher accuracy and reduced systematic errors. This improvement is particularly evident in the ϕ resolution, where the traditional method exhibits a noticeable splitting in the residuals, which are effectively mitigated by the neural network's reconstruction capabilities.

To further assess the performance of the neural network in transverse momentum reconstruction, the p_T resolution was examined as a function of the reconstructed p_T^{RECO} , as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Comparison of the relative transverse momentum resolution, $\Delta p_T/p_T$, between the L1 trigger system (L1) and the neural network (NN) reconstruction as a function of the reconstructed muon transverse momentum, p_T^{RECO} . The plots illustrate the performance for different stub configurations: (a) 2 stubs, (b) 3 stubs, and (c) 4 stubs. The results demonstrate that the neural network achieves a more consistent and precise p_T reconstruction across the entire p_T spectrum, with narrower uncertainty bands and lower fluctuations, particularly at lower p_T values. Interestingly, the 3NN and 4NN configurations perform well but not as well as the 2NN, which is due to the increasing precision of the Kalman Filter used in the traditional reconstruction method as the number of stubs increases.

This plot compares the relative p_T resolution, $\Delta p_T/p_T$, for the L1 trigger system and the neural network. The results demonstrate that the neural network achieves a more consistent and precise p_T reconstruction across the entire p_T spectrum. The shaded regions in the plot represent the uncertainty bands for each method, where the neural network exhibits significantly narrower bands, indicating lower uncertainty and higher reliability. Conversely, the L1 trigger system shows larger fluctuations, particularly at lower p_T values. This consistency in performance underscores the robustness of the neural network approach in maintaining high precision across different p_T ranges. Interestingly, the 3NN and 4NN configurations perform well, but not as effectively as the 2NN configuration. This is likely because, as the number of stubs increases, the Kalman Filter used in the traditional reconstruction method becomes more precise, making further gains from the neural network less significant.

6.2 Conclusion

The integration of neural networks into the CMS Level-1 trigger system represents a significant advancement in the evolution of data acquisition and processing techniques in high-energy physics experiments. By leveraging the power of machine learning and modern hardware accelerators, the CMS experiment is well-positioned to meet the challenges of the HL-LHC era, potentially setting new standards for real-time data processing in particle physics.

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